

Thermal Behaviour of Morpholinium Magnesium Sulphate (morphH)₂SO₄.MgSO₄.24H₂O.

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A double sulphate of morpholinium and magnesium of composition (morphH)₂SO₄.MgSO₄.24H₂O has been isolated and its thermal behaviour was studied by thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis techniques. The double sulphate after dehydration and decomposition of morpholinium moiety, gives a stable phase, MgS₂O₇, in the temperature range 520-900°. When MgS₂O₇ is exposed to humid atmosphere it gives MgS₂O₇.8H₂O which dehydrates on heating to 350°.

MORPHOLINE (morph) is a heterocyclic base of moderate strength and can easily be protonated to give -onium type salts. Morpholinium sulphate like ammonium sulphate, is expected to form double sulphates with several divalent and trivalent metal sulphates. During the course of our investigations on these systems¹ a double sulphate of morpholinium and magnesium of composition, (morphH)₂SO₄.MgSO₄.24H₂O has been isolated. This paper deals with the thermal behaviour of (morphH)₂SO₄.MgSO₄.24H₂O as studied by thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis techniques.

Experimental

(MorphH)₂SO₄ was prepared by neutralizing 50% a queous morpholine with 6N H₂SO₄ and concentrating the resultant solution. Colourless crystals of (morphH)₂SO₄ were separated out. The solutions containing (morphH)₂SO₄ and MgSO₄.7H₂O in equimolar amounts were evaporated to small volume and on cooling prismatic crystals of (morphH)₂SO₄.MgSO₄.24H₂O were separated out. The crystals were collected on a filter, washed with acetone and dried in a desiccator. Found : N, 3.57; 3, 7.37; Mg, 3.18%, required for C₈H₈₀N₂O₃₄S₂Mg, N, 3.43; S, 7.85; Mg, 2.98%.

Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a Stanton recording thermobalance at a linear heating rate of 6° min. Differential thermal analysis was made on Netzsch recording differential thermal analyser using inert alumina as reference material and a heating rate of 10° min. The X-ray powder patterns were taken using CuK_α radiation on a 114.6 mm diameter camera. The infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 257 infrared spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The thermogravimetric curve of (morphH)₂SO₄.MgSO₄.24H₂O given in Fig. 1, clearly indicates that the dehydration of the double salt begins around 70° and 12 molecules of water are lost by 220° (portion

AB). Dehydration continues on further rise in temperature giving apparently the anhydrous double sulphate at 320° (portion BC) which is closely followed by the decomposition of morpholinium moiety till the temperature reached 520°. The weight loss recorded

Fig. 1. Thermogravimetric curves of (morphH)₂SO₄.MgSO₄.24H₂O (ABCDEF) and MgS₂O₇.8H₂O (QJRST).

at this stage was 75.6% and this is compatible with the value namely, 75.72%, if the residue were to have the composition MgS₂O₇. (In a separate experiment, the double sulphate was heated upto 550° and the product was analyzed for Mg and S. Found : Mg, 11.88; S, 32.34%; required for MgS₂O₇, Mg, 12.13; S, 32.00%). MgS₂O₇ was stable upto 900° beyond which it decomposed to MgO whose formation was complete at 1100°. The weight loss observed was 95% and expected for the formation of MgO 95.05%. The MgO phase was also confirmed by its X-ray pattern and chemical analysis.

THERMAL BEHAVIOUR OF MORPHOLINIUM MAGNESIUM SULPHATE

Several endothermic peaks (Fig. 2a), were observed in the DTA run of the double salt namely, at 100°, 130°, 160°, 190°, 280°, 365° and 420°. These are ascribed to stepwise dehydration below 300° and decomposition of morpholinium moiety above 350°. An exothermic peak noticed at 660° is probably due to the crystallization of MgS_2O_7 . This peak may

Fig. 2. Differential thermal analysis of $(\text{morphH})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (a) and $\text{MgS}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (b).

not be due to first order phase transition as no endothermic peak is observed around this temperature on cooling the sample from 700° to 500°. The endothermic peak at 1000° is due to the decomposition of MgS_2O_7 to give MgO .

When the solid, having the composition, MgS_2O_7 , obtained on heating the double sulphate at 550°, was exposed to humid atmosphere, it was found that 8 moles of water were absorbed per mole of MgS_2O_7 within 24 hr. No additional increase in weight was noticed on keeping the sample for days. The chemical analysis of this product gave Mg, 7.21; S, 18.36%, required for $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot \text{SO}_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Mg, 7.06; S, 18.61%. This hydrated phase though has the overall chemical composition $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot \text{SO}_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ its formulation as such is most unlikely. It can be given two plausible formulations namely, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{MgS}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Since $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ itself is known on heating to get converted to MgSO_4 , " $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ " would only be expected to behave similarly. $\text{MgS}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on the other hand, may lose water on heating to give back MgS_2O_7 phase. Since this is what was experimentally observed it is most probable that the hydrated phase is $\text{MgS}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the double sulphate and of $\text{MgS}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot \text{SO}_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are given in Table 1. The thermogravimetric curve of $\text{MgS}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ given in Fig. 1 shows that 7 molecules of water are lost in the temperature range 70° to 200° (portion PQ). On further rise in temperature, the anhydrous phase, MgS_2O_7 was obtained at 350°; weight loss found 42% and expected 41.8%. Chemical analysis of this product also confirmed the composition as MgS_2O_7 . Above 900°, the anhydrous phase decomposed to MgO (portion ST). Four endothermic peaks, ascribed to stepwise dehydration, were observed at 100°, 135°, 170° and 305° (Fig. 2b) on heating $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot \text{SO}_3$

TABLE 1. PARTIAL X-RAY POWDER DATA FOR THE DOUBLE SULPHATE AND THE HYDRATED PHASE (d_{hkl} IN Å)

$(\text{morphH})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{MgS}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$
5.01(s)	5.47(m)
4.27(s)	4.99(m)
3.53(s)	4.22(s)
3.36(w)	4.06(s)
3.09(m)	3.62(m)
2.78(s)	3.43(m)
2.56(m)	3.16(w)
2.28(m)	2.88(s)
2.09(w)	2.78(m)
1.94(s)	2.55(w)
1.78(m)	2.31(s)
	2.06(w)
	1.85(m)

s = strong m = medium w = weak

$8\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The exothermic peak at 660° is probably due to the crystallization of MgS_2O_7 phase and the endothermic peak at 1000° is the decomposition of the latter to give MgO .

The infrared frequencies observed for $\text{MgS}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are 3300, 1600 cm^{-1} (due to H_2O) and 1052, 1012, 980 and 700 cm^{-1} (due to S-O groups).

The stable phase, MgS_2O_7 , observed in the temperature range 520°–900° is hygroscopic and absorbs water readily in humid atmosphere. Alkali metal hydrogen sulphates give respective metal pyrosulphates on thermal decomposition². Thus, the phase obtained at room temperature may be $\text{Mg}(\text{HSO}_4)_2 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The TG and DTA curves of $\text{MgS}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ indicate the stepwise removal of 8 molecules of water. Infrared frequencies observed (as reported above) also indicate the lowering of T_d symmetry of SO_4 group in $\text{MgS}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It is not clear how MgS_2O_7 forms as a distinct phase during the decomposition of $(\text{morphH})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Attempts to prepare either $\text{Mg}(\text{HSO}_4)_2$ or MgS_2O_7 from $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ interactions were unsuccessful. Also, the thermal decomposition of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot (\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ gave only MgSO_4 as the intermediate product and not MgS_2O_7 . When $\text{MgS}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in excess water, it was not possible to recover it by evaporation of the solution. In fact under these conditions, the system would be the same as a $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ system from which no compounds containing Mg : S ratio exceeding unity have been reported in literature.

References

1. M. R. UDUFA and G. ARAVAMUDAN, to be published.
2. R. C. BRASTED, Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry, D. Van Nostrand Co., Inc., New York, 1961, Vol. VIII, p. 209.